

WHAT CAN I DO?

Rest does not cure tendinopathy, but exercising to the point of feeling pain in the tendon is also not helpful, so keeping up a walking programme that does not aggravate your pain will be worthwhile.

Walk on the flat, avoid hills and keep stairs to a minimum until your pain settles. Start with 10 minutes of walking and as your pain improves gradually increase your activity levels.

Applying heat to the hip and buttock can also provide relief.

LEAP-IRELAND PROJECT

The Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland is conducting research to answer important questions about lateral hip pain.

The clinical trial that you are enrolled in will determine which of the most commonly used treatments works best.

For the findings of the study to be worthwhile, you must keep to the treatment which you have been allocated.

If you have any concerns or questions about the trial, please contact the Trial Manager, Dr Sania Almousa at the Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland on: Saniaalmousa@rcsi.com or the Principal Investigator, Prof Helen French on: hfrench@rcsi.com

This information leaflet has been adapted, with permission from Prof Bill Vincenzino, University of Queensland, Australia, who was the lead investigator in the LEAP trial.

Lateral Hip Pain

LEAP-IRELAND FEASIBILITY CLINICAL TRIAL

The LEAP-Ireland study is a modification of the LEAP trial in Australia

LATERAL HIP PAIN

WHAT IS IT?

Lateral hip pain is pain that originates at the side of the hip, over the bony prominence called the greater trochanter. The main area of pain will occur around this bone, but commonly extends down the side of the thigh, and even into the top of the lower leg, below the knee. Pain may also extend a way forward into the groin, or back into the buttock.

It is often worse at night lying on either side, and may be aggravated by walking, particularly uphill and stairs, standing on one leg to dress, prolonged sitting, and there is often some pain and stiffness for the first few steps after rising to stand.

The condition has historically been diagnosed as 'trochanteric bursitis', however recently researchers have shown there to be problems of cells, collagen tissue and small blood vessels in the tendons of the buttock muscles - gluteus medius and minimus.

Gluteus Minimus
Gluteus Medius

WHY DO I HAVE IT?

Tendon health depends on the loads they bear on a regular basis, and either too much or too little loading can be problematic. For example, an athlete may overload the tendon and end up with tendon problems, whereas those who are not physically active may well suffer gradual tendon deterioration.

Either way the tendon health suffers and eventually pain is experienced when the weakened tendon is exposed to a range of possible factors, such as a rapid increase in loading that might occur with suddenly increasing training loads, or even taking up walking, particularly up hills and stairs, or with a slip or fall directly landing on the side of the hip.

Sometimes you may not be able to put your finger on a single factor as it might have occurred as a result of an accumulation of a number of small things, for example a gradual increase in weight over time and a reduction in general fitness.